

Novel scalable mesoporous silica-assisted synthesis of high-quality ϵ -Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles revealing extraordinarily high coercivity

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ABSTRACT

A new, scalable synthesis of ϵ -Fe₂O₃, an intermediate polymorph of iron oxide exhibiting a giant coercive field (H_C) was proposed. This study focuses on the preparation of ϵ -Fe₂O₃ through the co-precipitation of magnetite nanoparticles, their simultaneous coating with mesoporous silica, and air-annealing at sintering temperatures ranging from 1050 to 1125 °C. Structural and magnetic measurements were conducted to identify the optimal conditions for critical parameters of the synthesis, including silica content, annealing temperature and time. These conditions resulted in the production of nearly single-phase ϵ -Fe₂O₃ (over 95 %) with an exceptionally large coercivity of 22 kOe without any additional metal doping. This achievement is attributed to the mesoporous silica coating, which altered the parameters of the heat-induced phase transformation pathway when compared with the silica-coated precursor. The mesoporous silica coating resulted in improving the ϵ -Fe₂O₃ stability during thermal treatment while the silica coating of magnetite particles achieved only 75 % purity at the same conditions.

1. Introduction

Iron(III) oxides, which belong to the most extensively studied nanomaterials due to their versatile applications across various fields, exist in five crystalline polymorphs: α -Fe₂O₃ (hematite), β -Fe₂O₃, γ -Fe₂O₃ (maghemite), ϵ -Fe₂O₃, and the high-pressure stabilized ζ -Fe₂O₃, whose different crystal structures result in their specific physical behaviours [1,2]. Among them, ϵ -Fe₂O₃ has emerged as particularly intriguing owing to its exceptional magnetic characteristics, notably a coercive field of up to 20 kOe at room temperature, [3], a high Curie transition temperature of around 850 K [3–6], room-temperature ferroelectric and electric properties [7], and the efficient absorption of electromagnetic radiation in millimetre wavelengths (~100–200 GHz) [8]. These properties are closely tied to its orthorhombic crystal structure, characterized by significant magnetocrystalline anisotropy, which contrasts with the isotropic crystal structures of the other iron oxide polymorphs (α and γ -Fe₂O₃) [3,6,9,10]. These attributes make ϵ -Fe₂O₃ a rare and valuable material for applications requiring robust magnetic performance. Consequently, ϵ -Fe₂O₃ has gained attention for use in

high-density magnetic recording media and information storage [11], permanent magnets [3], electric/magnetic field-tunable devices [3,5,12], millimetre-wave absorption [13], ultra-high field magnetic resonance imaging [14], or magnetic hyperthermia [15].

Despite these promising properties, the synthesis of pure ϵ -Fe₂O₃ remains challenging due to its metastable nature. Typically, ϵ -Fe₂O₃ forms through a temperature-assisted phase transition pathway: γ -Fe₂O₃ → ϵ -Fe₂O₃ → α -Fe₂O₃, where the formation and conversion of ϵ -Fe₂O₃ to thermodynamically more stable α -Fe₂O₃ occurs at similar temperatures [16,17]. A key strategy to enhance phase stability involves the application of a silica protective layer around γ -Fe₂O₃ nanoparticle cores or incorporating a Fe-source into the silica matrix, which effectively prevents their transformation into α -Fe₂O₃ across a broad temperature range (900–1400 °C, depending on particle size [1]). Silica confinement limits particle growth and phase transitions, facilitating the stabilization of ϵ -Fe₂O₃. Several synthesis approaches have been developed for ϵ -Fe₂O₃ phase preparation, leading to the formation of sphere-like [14,18] or rod-like [4,19,20] nanoparticles, nanowires [21], and thin film structures [22–24]. Synthetic parameters such as the

Abbreviations: NPs, Nanoparticles; TEOS, Tetraorthosilane; CTAC, cetyltrimethylammonium chloride; TEM, Transmission electron microscopy; XRD, X-ray powder diffraction; MLC, a mean coherence length; SQUID, superconducting quantum interference device; ZFC, Zero-field-cooled; FC, Field cooled.

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choice of iron precursors, the presence of additives, silica coating, and annealing conditions critically influence the resulting ϵ -Fe₂O₃ purity, size, and magnetic properties. However, only a few works have achieved products with ϵ -Fe₂O₃ purity higher than 90 % [18,25,26] and with a large coercivity of 20 kOe [18]. In this regard, it has been reported that the addition of certain cations (such as Ba²⁺ [4,21], Sr³⁺ [16], Ga²⁺ [13,27], Y³⁺ [28], Sc³⁺ [29], and Rh²⁺ [5,30]) during the synthesis appears to stabilize the ϵ -Fe₂O₃ phase which can be attributed to their unique crystal structure and the presence of defects or impurities in the crystal lattice [5]. Furthermore, ϵ -Fe₂O₃ thin films with Ba²⁺ and Rh²⁺ substitutions displayed exceptionally large coercive fields of 23.4 kOe and 35 kOe, respectively, when their nanoparticles (NPs) were perfectly aligned by an external magnetic field [19,30]. Despite these advances, existing synthesis methods face significant limitations. Among these, the sol-gel methods [11,16,18–20,28,31,32], although effective, often include extended gelation times of silica matrix (several days), which hinders aggregation and enhances the thermal stability of particles [18,25]. Impregnation techniques typically suffer from low Fe:SiO ratios [5,26,33,34], and some methods require harsh conditions for silica removal post-synthesis [9,20].

Here, we present a novel and scalable synthesis route for high-quality ϵ -Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles embedded in a mesoporous silica matrix. Our approach utilizes the co-precipitation method to generate magnetite (Fe₃O₄) nanoparticles directly within silica or mesoporous silica, followed by controlled thermal annealing to achieve ϵ -Fe₂O₃ formation. Although precipitation and co-precipitation methods are simple and widely used for the synthesis of iron-bearing materials, their application to ϵ -Fe₂O₃ synthesis has been limited, with prior studies [35,36] achieving no more than 51 % ϵ -phase content. In this study, we systematically investigate and optimize the parameters governing co-precipitation, subsequent silica or mesoporous silica matrix formation, and thermal treatment protocol. The impact of cetyltrimethylammonium chloride (CTAC) as a moderator of mesoporous silica formation is evaluated using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and gas sorption analysis (BET). The optimization of silica and mesoporous silica content, along with thermal treatment conditions, is analysed via X-ray powder diffraction (XRD). The formation of ϵ -Fe₂O₃ with high phase purity and excellent magnetic properties is demonstrated through comparative phase composition (XRD) and magnetic measurements. Our methodology addresses the limitations of conventional approaches, offering a cost-effective, efficient, and reproducible pathway for the synthesis of ϵ -Fe₂O₃ suitable for future technological applications.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Silica and mesoporous silica coated magnetite nanoparticles preparation and the subsequent thermal treatment experiments

A co-precipitation method was employed to synthesize magnetite nanoparticles (NPs), which served as a precursor for ϵ -Fe₂O₃. To enhance the stability of these NPs during thermal treatment, a silica coating was performed immediately after the formation of magnetite NPs in the single reaction mixture. Briefly, to prepare mesoporous silica-coated magnetite NPs, 1.87 g of FeCl₂·4H₂O (Sigma-Aldrich) and 4.02 g of FeCl₃·6H₂O (Sigma-Aldrich) were dissolved in 18 mL of deionized water in a 50 mL Falcon tube, followed by the addition of 16 mL of cetyltrimethylammonium chloride (CTAC, 25 % w/w in H₂O, Sigma-Aldrich), resulting in yellow gel formation. Subsequently, 7.2 mL of ammonia (Ammonia solution p.a. 24 %, Penta) was added and vigorously shaken by hand to dissolve the gel. The solution was placed on a 360° multi-functional tube rotator (PTR-60, Grant USA INC., USA) and mixed at 25 rpm for 1 h. Then, an aliquot of tetraethoxysilane (TEOS, Sigma-Aldrich), was added according to Table S1 in the supporting information (SI), and the reaction was continued for an additional 2 h on the orbital shaker (samples M_mSiO(1-14)). For silica-coated magnetite

NPs, the CTAC solution was replaced with deionized water as outlined in Table S1 (samples M_SiO

(1-5)). The magnetic products were isolated via magnetic separation and washed three times with 200 mL of ethanol to prevent foaming, three times with 200 mL of deionized water, and once with ethanol before being dried at 80 °C. Finally, both silica-coated and mesoporous silica-coated magnetite NPs were annealed at 250 °C for 2 h to remove residual solvents and oxidize magnetite to the maghemite phase. For these prepared precursors, the contents of maghemite and silica were determined and heat-induced phase transformation at 1100 °C was performed. The percentage of silica in the precursor was determined gravimetrically as the difference between the mass of the entire composite after annealing at 250 °C for 2 h and the mass of maghemite formed after a 1 h reaction (corresponding to the time required for the precipitation of magnetite from iron salts) followed by annealing at 250 °C for 2 h (which leads to the oxidation of magnetite nanoparticles to maghemite). The obtained γ -Fe₂O₃:SiO₂ mass ratio is given in Table S1 in the SI. For the heat-induced phase transformation of prepared precursors, 0.5 g of each sample was put into a ceramic crucible and placed in the oven (LM312.27, Linn High Therm, Germany) tempered at 1100 °C for 3 h. After that, the hot samples were taken out of the oven and left to cool down to laboratory temperature.

For specific surface area analysis, determination of pore size distribution, and temperature and time optimization of air-annealing, a sample was prepared with a 10-fold higher scale of all reaction components, with and without CTAC marked as M_mSiO and M_SiO, respectively, and using 66 mL of TEOS for mesoporous silica coating (Table S1).

For magnetic measurements, four samples of 0.5 g each were placed in a preheated oven at the appropriate temperatures of 1050 °C, 1075 °C, 1100 °C, and 1125 °C, respectively, and one sample was taken out at the appropriate time (1, 3, 5, and 10 h, respectively).

Silica removal was performed by NaOH etching. To determine the sufficient conditions, 0.1–1 M NaOH (Penta) and incubation at 80 °C for 1 h in a sonication bath were applied. The treated samples were three times washed using ethanol and dried at 80 °C.

2.2. Characterisation

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was used to capture microscopic images with a JEM2010 (JEOL Ltd., Japan) microscope operating at 200 kV, which has a point-to-point resolution of 1.9 Å. X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) measurement at room temperature was done with an Aeris diffractometer (Malvern PANalytical, B. V., Netherlands) equipped with iron filtered Co K α radiation source and operating in Bragg-Brentano parafocussing geometry. Powder samples were placed on a zero-background silicon sample holder. In-situ XRD experiments at high-temperature were performed using HTK 1200 N (Anton Paar GmbH, Austria) chamber mounted to Empyrean diffractometer (Malvern PANalytical, B.V., Netherlands). The diffractometer operates in Bragg-Brentano parafocussing geometry and is equipped with iron filtered Co K α radiation source and programmable divergence and diffracted beam antiscatter slits irradiating constant area of the sample. Approximately 70 mg of the material was placed in the sample holder and continuously heated from room-temperature up to 1100 °C (with temperature increase 60 °C/min). Subsequently, the sample was isothermally annealed for 10 h at 1100 °C in the atmosphere of ambient air and the diffraction patterns were acquired every 10 min to elucidate mechanism and kinetics of the material transformation. All XRD data were processed using High Score Plus software (Malvern PANalytical, B. V. Netherlands) in conjunction with the PDF-5+ database. The quantification, crystallographic structural parameters, and crystallite sizes (MCL) of the identified phases were calculated using Rietveld refinement carried in High Score Plus software, version 4.8. The commercially available standards SRM640 (Si) and SRM660 (LaB₆) were used for the evaluation of the line positions and instrumental line broadening,

respectively. The specific surface area and pore size distribution of samples were estimated by means of N_2 adsorption/desorption measurements at 77 K on a volumetric gas adsorption analyser (Autosorb iQ XR, Anton-Paar Quanta Tec, USA) up to 0.965 p/p_0 . Prior to the analysis, the sample was degassed under high vacuum (10^{-7} Pa) at 50 °C for 16 h, while high purity N_2 (99.999 %) and He (≥ 99.9999 %) gases were used for the measurements. The Brunauer–Emmett–Teller surface area (BET) was determined with respect to Rouquerol criteria for N_2 isotherm [37]. Pore size distribution was obtained using QSDFT-based method [38].

Magnetic measurements of samples after silica removal were performed using a superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID, MPMS XL-7, Quantum Design, USA). Hysteresis loops were collected at temperature of 300 K in external magnetic fields ranging from -7 T to $+7$ T.

3. Results and discussion

The synthesis of magnetite NPs is based on ammonia-assisted coprecipitation of Fe(II) and Fe(III) chlorides. The mean X-ray coherence length (MCL) of the prepared magnetite NPs, corresponding to a crystallite size, is calculated to be 12 nm. In the synthesis, ammonia plays a crucial role in both, magnetite and silica formation when TEOS is added directly to a reaction mixture containing the as-synthesized magnetite NPs, without any prior washing steps. To optimize the synthesis and compare the effects of SiO_2 and mesoporous SiO_2 coatings, precursors with varying percentages of the silica matrix were prepared (Fig. 1a and

b, respectively). The increasing thickness of the coatings was also confirmed by TEM (Fig. S1 in supporting information). During the process of optimizing the preparation of silica-coated ϵ - Fe_2O_3 , it is observed that the silica content significantly influences the phase composition of iron oxide after thermal treatment, as shown in Fig. 1c.

Specifically, a purity of 74 % for the ϵ - Fe_2O_3 phase is achieved for silica-coated NPs when the SiO_2 content reach 58 % w/w. Contrary to expectations, increasing the silica content does not result in higher yields of the epsilon phase. The addition of CTAC, a surfactant that plays a crucial role in stabilizing NPs during synthesis and enabling the formation of a mesoporous silica structure [39], results in a distinctly different distribution of Fe_2O_3 polymorphs. While the thermal treatment of silica-coated magnetite results in the formation of two polymorphs, ϵ - Fe_2O_3 and α - Fe_2O_3 , an unreacted phase γ - Fe_2O_3 , is present when mesoporous silica-coated magnetite NPs (silica content above 50 % w/w) are thermally annealed under the same conditions (Fig. 1d). Moreover, higher purity of 87 % ϵ - Fe_2O_3 is already achieved at 36 % w/w silica content, and the highest ϵ - Fe_2O_3 content of 98 % is observed at silica content of 50 % w/w. The higher silica contents in CTAC assisted synthesis are found to improve the stability of γ - Fe_2O_3 and completely suppress the formation of α - Fe_2O_3 under the given conditions of thermal annealing (Fig. 1d).

The effect of CTAC on the silica structure is examined by comparing the adsorption-desorption isotherms of silica coated NPs (M_SiO, silica content 47.0 ± 0.4 w/w) and CTAC-assisted silica coated NPs (M_mSiO, silica content 47.7 ± 0.2 w/w) (Fig. 2a).

Fig. 1. The weight percentage (w/w) of maghemite and silica content in silica-coated samples (Fig. 1a) and mesoporous silica-coated samples (Fig. 1b) prior to annealing at 250 °C for 2 h. Contents of three Fe_2O_3 crystalline phases calculated by Rietveld refinement (XRD) for silica (c) and mesoporous silica (d) coated precursors air-annealed at 1100 °C for 3 h.

Fig. 2. Adsorption-desorption isotherms (a), pore size distribution (b), and TEM images (scale bar is 20 nm) of iron oxide NPs coated with mesoporous silica before (c) and after (d) thermal annealing (M_mSiO, M_mSiO_1100, respectively), and NPs coated with silica before (e) and after (f) thermal annealing (M_SiO and M_SiO_1100, respectively).

The adsorption-desorption isotherms of M_SiO have a shape corresponding to the type III, whereas the adsorption-desorption isotherms of M_mSiO belong to the type II according to the IUPAC classification [40]. Moreover, both isotherms exhibit a hysteresis, which shape is indicating the porosity of both materials. The pore structure of both samples can be clearly seen in Fig. 2b, where a macroporous structure is common to both samples, while the presence of pore size between 20 and 40 nm is exclusive to the M_mSiO sample, indicating a mesoporous structure of silica. This mesoporous structure is also reflected in the specific surface area, calculated to be 121 m²/g for M_mSiO, whereas the specific surface area of M_SiO is 50 m²/g. The TEM images of M_mSiO (Fig. 2c) and M_SiO (Fig. 2e) confirm the different morphologies of the silica coating with and without CTAC, respectively. The presence of CTAC in the synthesis of M_mSiO results in a more rippled surface of silica (Fig. 2c), whereas M_SiO has a core-shell structure (Fig. 2e). The thermal annealing (1100 °C, 3 h) of both materials (M_mSiO and M_SiO) results in a transformation of the morphology of silica (samples M_mSiO_1100 and M_SiO_1100, respectively), which no longer forms a shell coating around the iron oxide NPs (Fig. 2d and f, respectively). The silica transformation after thermal annealing is confirmed by the adsorption-desorption isotherms of M_mSiO_1100 and M_SiO_1100 (Fig. 2a), where both isotherms are type III and exhibit lower intensities of pore volume values than M_mSiO and M_SiO. Moreover, thermal annealing affected the mesoporous structure of M_mSiO, and only macroporous structured silica is identified in the sample M_mSiO_1100 (Fig. 2b). The specific surface areas of thermally treated samples M_mSiO_1100 and M_SiO_1100 are 29 m²/g and 24 m²/g, respectively.

The in-situ X-ray diffraction annealing study of M_SiO and M_mSiO at 1100 °C confirms the impact of mesoporous silica on the pathway of Fe₂O₃ phase formation (Fig. 3). The γ -Fe₂O₃ phase of the silica coated precursor M_SiO is fully transformed within 40 min of thermal annealing, with the content of the ϵ -Fe₂O₃ phase not exceeding 70 %. Simultaneously, the ϵ -Fe₂O₃ phase begins to slowly transform into α -Fe₂O₃ after several minutes of annealing, and the content of the α -Fe₂O₃ phase (31 %) increases over the duration of annealing (Fig. 3a). In contrast, the

mesoporous silica coated precursor M_mSiO exhibits higher stability (with the full transformation of the γ -Fe₂O₃ phase taking more than an hour) and a higher yield of the ϵ -Fe₂O₃ phase, which reaches 95 % (Fig. 3b). The noticeable transformation of the ϵ -Fe₂O₃ phase to α -Fe₂O₃ occurs after 1 h of thermal annealing.

The thermal stability of M_SiO (Fig. 3c), evaluated across temperatures ranging from 250 °C to 1100 °C after 2 h exposition, revealing instability starting at 700 °C, where γ -Fe₂O₃ partially transforms into α -Fe₂O₃. The content of α -Fe₂O₃ increases over 30 % by exposition to 900 °C, likely due to uneven silica matrix coating around the particles. The annealing of M_SiO at 800 °C resulted in ϵ -Fe₂O₃ formation, though its purity is compromised by α -Fe₂O₃ (formed at lower temperatures) and residual γ -Fe₂O₃, which persists in the sample up to 1000 °C. By contrast, the thermal stability of M_mSiO at the same condition solely reveals the γ -to ϵ -to α -phase-transition pathway (Fig. 3d). The iron oxide nanoparticles encapsulated in mesoporous silica maintain the γ -Fe₂O₃ phase constancy and MCL of approximately 10 nm up to 800 °C. Crystal growth is observed above 900 °C with these crystals being formed by the ϵ -Fe₂O₃ phase (the determined MCL is 18 nm), which still represents a minority fraction of the material under the given annealing conditions. The ϵ -Fe₂O₃ phase becomes the majority phase of the material after thermal treatment above 1000 °C (after 2 h of annealing) and is characterized by an MCL ranging between 20 and 40 nm. The α -Fe₂O₃ phase appears at temperatures above 1050 °C, which may contribute to the beginning of the instability of mesoporous silica; its transformation at 1100 °C is confirmed by TEM and BET analysis, as it was discussed above. All samples annealed at temperatures between 250 °C and 1000 °C were subsequently thermally decomposed at 1100 °C for 3 h to reveal the impact of organic impurities (i.e., the residual CTAC in mesoporous silica), which should be removed at temperatures between 250 °C and 700 °C [41]. The purity of ϵ -Fe₂O₃ in the M_SiO sample reached a maximum of 65 % (Fig. 3e) due to the presence of the α -Fe₂O₃ phase, which forms at lower temperatures (700–900 °C), as shown in Fig. 3c. Besides, the analysis does not reveal a significant impact of pre-annealing temperature for M_mSiO (Fig. 3f), with only a slight

Fig. 3. Quantification of time-dependent crystalline iron oxide phases composition calculated from in-situ XRD monitoring of isothermal annealing of M₂SiO (a) and M₂mSiO (b) at 1100 °C for 10 h. Thermal stability of M₂SiO (c) and M₂mSiO (d) as XRD evaluated phase-composition at temperatures ranging between 250 and 1000 °C after 2 h of exposition. Phase composition of post-thermal annealing of M₂SiO (pre-annealed in the range between 250 °C and 1000 °C for 2 h) (e) and M₂mSiO (pre-annealed in the range between 250 °C and 1000 °C for 2 h) (f) at 1100 °C for 3 h.

reduction in ϵ -Fe₂O₃ content (from 95 % to 91 %) observed as the temperature of annealing increases from 250 °C to 1000 °C.

Fe₂O₃ crystals entrapped in the silica matrix of M₂SiO (Fig. 4a) and M₂mSiO (Fig. 4d) after thermal treatment (1100 °C, 3 h) can be obtained by etching the silica matrix under appropriate conditions. For this purpose, NaOH-assisted etching was tested using concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 1 M at 80 °C for 1 h. The sufficient conditions of silica etching for M₂SiO and M₂mSiO were determined by TEM (Fig. 4b and e, respectively) and XRD analysis (Fig. 4c and f, respectively), which confirming the removal of the characteristic amorphous silica glass hump (visible on XRD diffractograms as a broad hump at angles between 20 and 30° 2 θ). Interestingly, it was found that even a 0.5 M NaOH solution can remove the silica from the both silica coated and mesoporous silica coated samples, which is several times lower concentration than described in earlier studies [20].

The purity and magnetic properties of the ϵ -Fe₂O₃ phase can be further tuned by optimizing the temperature and time parameters of the

precursor's thermal treatment. For this purpose, temperature and time parameters were designed to be within the 1050–1125 °C and 1–10 h, respectively, based on the previous results (Fig. 3d) and the available literature [11,25]. Fig. S2(a–d) in the SI and Table 1 show XRD patterns and crystalline phase composition of the samples. All patterns exhibit the characteristic broad hump between 20 and 30° 2 θ , representing amorphous silica, along with several peaks which can be assigned to crystalline phases of γ -Fe₂O₃, ϵ -Fe₂O₃, and α -Fe₂O₃. The content of ϵ -Fe₂O₃ over 95 % of the iron-bearing phases was achieved for the temperature range of 1050 °C–1100 °C. When the lower temperature of 1050 °C is used for phase transformation, a longer time is required (more than 5 h) for the complete transformation of γ -Fe₂O₃. In general, the use of higher annealing temperatures reduces the time required for the transformation of γ -Fe₂O₃, and conversely, the formation of α -Fe₂O₃ was significantly more pronounced. The optimal annealing times at 1075 °C and 1100 °C were determined to be 5 and 1 h, respectively, when phase composition in favour of ϵ -Fe₂O₃ is considered. The patterns of samples

Fig. 4. TEM images (scale bar is 50 nm) of thermally treated (1100 °C for 3 h) M_SSiO and M_mSiO before (a) and (d), respectively, and after 0.5 M NaOH-assisted etching (b) and (e), respectively. The impact of NaOH molarity on silica etching determined by XRD analysis for M_SSiO (c) and M_mSiO (f).

Table 1

Temperature and time parameters of air-annealing experiments, the crystalline phase composition supplemented by MCL values obtained from XRD measurements using Rietveld refinement, and the magnetic properties characterized by values of coercivity (H_C), maximum magnetization (M_{max}), and remanent magnetization (M_R).

Conditions of annealing		XRD measurements						Magnetic measurements		
T	t	γ -Fe ₂ O ₃		ε -Fe ₂ O ₃		α -Fe ₂ O ₃		M_{max} (50 000 Oe)	H_C	M_R
(°C)	(hours)	(%)	MCL (nm)	(%)	MCL (nm)	(%)	MCL (nm)	(emu/g)	(Oe)	(emu/g)
1050	1	7.7	20	89.5	26	2.8	31	22.9	1.6	6.4
	3	4.1	19	92.7	28	3.2	37	20.7	10.3	7.1
	5	1.5	42	98.0	27	0.5	–	19.8	14.9	7.5
	10	–	–	96.0	35	4.0	65	17.7	22.1	8.3
1075	1	–	–	93.0	29	7.0	19	20.7	9.4	7.6
	3	–	–	94.0	35	6.0	25	17.9	21.4	8.7
	5	–	–	95.0	34	5.0	55	17.7	21.9	9.0
	10	–	–	90.0	43	10.0	81	16.2	22.6	8.4
1100	1	–	–	96.0	34	4.0	36	19.0	20.3	8.7
	3	–	–	95.0	36	5.0	62	17.0	22.2	9.0
	5	–	–	93.0	39	7.0	72	16.3	22.3	8.7
	10	–	–	80.0	43	20.0	64	14.2	23.3	7.6
1125	1	–	–	91.9	38	8.1	63	17.4	22.0	8.8
	3	–	–	79.1	55	20.9	67	14.2	22.1	7.4
	5 ^a	–	–	57.7	56	40.4	61	10.5	22.1	5.4
	10 ^b	–	–	14.2	55	68.3	70	4.6	22.0	2.1

^a 1.9 % of cristobalite.

^b 17.5 % of cristobalite.

annealed at 1125 °C are characterized by the presence of significant amounts of α -Fe₂O₃, while the quantity of ε -Fe₂O₃ rapidly decreases over time. Moreover, the crystalline phase of SiO₂ (cristobalite), appears after 5 h of annealing. This is attributed to the collapse of the silica coating in favour of the formation of a crystalline SiO₂ structure and the preferential formation of hematite.

Moreover, next to the discussion of phase composition by XRD analysis, the purity of ε -Fe₂O₃ can be well characterized from the viewpoint of its magnetic properties. The hysteresis curves of the samples annealed at different temperatures and times (Fig. 5) were measured after removing the silica layer via 1 M NaOH etching. The removal of the silica matrix was necessary due to its instability during

annealing, as confirmed by BET and XRD analyses. This instability was identified as a critical factor influencing the saturation magnetization, which is normalized to the mass of the studied material. Consequently, silica matrix removal results in a marked increase in saturation magnetization corresponding to the iron-bearing phases, while the coercivity remains unaffected (Fig. S3 in the SI).

The morphology of the hysteresis loops of the samples (Fig. 5) is determined by their composition and allows for the qualitative identification of the presence of Fe₂O₃-phases. The presence of γ -Fe₂O₃, even in minimal amounts, leads to a distinctive 'necking' in the hysteresis loop, attributable to its low coercivity value around 17 Oe, and is also indicated by an elevated saturation magnetization of approximately 69

Fig. 5. Hysteresis loops of samples, which were air-annealed at 1050 °C (a), 1075 °C (b), 1100 °C (c) and 1125 °C (d) for 1–10 h, collected at 300 K.

emu/g. On the contrary, the α -phase, being a weak ferromagnet with a saturation magnetization value around 2 emu/g, has a significant contribution to the overall magnetization of the sample when subjected to a magnetic field strength of 7 kOe [25]. Therefore, the values of saturation magnetization and coercivity (Table 1) together with the shape of hysteresis loops (Fig. 5) clearly identified the presence and content of the γ , ϵ , and α -phases, and correspond to the results from the XRD analysis (Table 1).

High-quality ϵ -Fe₂O₃ samples can be obtained under air-annealing conditions of 1050 °C (10 h), 1075 °C (5 h), and 1100 °C (3 h) where the samples reached 95 % purity and exhibited a coercivity of 22 kOe. Furthermore, the maximal coercivity of 23.3 kOe was determined for a sample annealed at 1100 °C for 10 h with 80 % purity of ϵ -Fe₂O₃ supplemented by 20 % hematite α -Fe₂O₃. These values of coercivity surpass the value of 20 kOe previously determined for pure ϵ -Fe₂O₃ [18,42] and are even higher than most doped ϵ -Fe₂O₃ materials where the substitution of ϵ -Fe₂O₃ by barium [4,11], yttrium [28], or strontium [17] resulted in materials having a coercivity of 20 kOe (Ba²⁺, Y³⁺) and 21.3 kOe (Sr²⁺). The higher coercive field of 27 kOe has been achieved only in rhodium-substituted ϵ -Fe₂O₃ prepared by impregnating mesoporous silica with iron and rhodium nitrates [5].

The achievement of such high coercivity values arises not only from the phase purity of ϵ -Fe₂O₃ but also from the attained crystal size, as evidenced by its correlation with the MCL values determined by XRD analysis (Table 1). Samples with ϵ -Fe₂O₃ MCL below 34 nm (annealed at 1050 °C for 1–5 h or 1075 °C for 1 h) exhibit pronounced hysteresis loops "necking", low coercivity (<15 kOe), and higher saturation magnetization. This suggests residual γ -Fe₂O₃ content and its incomplete phase transformation under these annealing conditions. Samples with ϵ -Fe₂O₃ MCL between 34 and 39 nm (annealed at 1050 °C for 10 h, 1075 °C for 3–10 h, or 1100 °C for 1–5 h) achieve higher coercivity (20.3–22.6 kOe); however, their saturation magnetization decreases

with increasing temperature and annealing time. This is attributed to the attainment of the optimal crystal size for ϵ -Fe₂O₃ at which γ -Fe₂O₃ is almost completely converted but the α -Fe₂O₃ begins to form. The highest coercivity (23.3 kOe) was observed in the sample annealed at 1100 °C for 10 h, indicating that the coercivity of ϵ -Fe₂O₃ could continue to increase with increasing MCL. However, this is accompanied by a simultaneous increase in the hematite content. Annealing at 1125 °C led to a further increase in the ϵ -Fe₂O₃ MCL, but the coercivity was only 22.0–22.1 kOe after annealing longer than 3 h, with a significant content of hematite. This confirms previous studies [43], which discuss an MCL around 40 nm as the upper size limit for achieving the maximum coercivity of the pure ϵ -Fe₂O₃.

It is well known that ϵ -Fe₂O₃ is viewed as an intermediate polymorph between γ -Fe₂O₃ and α -Fe₂O₃ [10] with significant thermal instability and the crucial importance of surface energy on its formation and existence [3,44]. The essential role in preventing aggregation and isolating the nanoparticles from each other is in the supporting medium such as a porous silica matrix which provides nucleating sites for the formation of ϵ -Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles. It was documented for sphere-like nanoobjects that crossing the ~30 nm threshold leads to the transformation to α -Fe₂O₃ polymorph and ϵ -Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles with larger sizes can be prepared in a stable form just with the addition of an appropriate amount of Group IIA metal ions [4,45,46]. In other words, the stabilization of ϵ -Fe₂O₃ in the proper range around 43 nm is crucial for the observation of the largest value of coercivity, 23.3 kOe, without any other substitution of other atoms to the crystal structure ϵ -Fe₂O₃ [47].

4. Conclusion

The preparation of ϵ -Fe₂O₃ samples is a multifaceted process that requires careful control of synthesis conditions to achieve the desired phase composition and material characteristics. The co-precipitation

synthesis of the precursor, silica and mesoporous-silica coated magnetite NPs, and the factors of its heat-induced phase transformation discussed here highlight the complexity of preparing this metastable iron oxide phase and the importance of characterization in confirming the successful preparation of ϵ -Fe₂O₃. Through this systematic study, the ϵ -Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles with a purity of over 95 % and a large coercivity of 22 kOe via a simple, fast and scalable process without utilizing stabilizing cation doping were obtained. Moreover, the highest published value of maximal coercivity of 23.3 kOe was detected for the pure, non-oriented ϵ -Fe₂O₃ phase. Thanks to the established critical parameters of the mesoporous silica-assisted co-precipitation synthesis, high-quality ϵ -Fe₂O₃ can find its utilization in applications such as permanent magnets, information storage, magnetic recording media or millimetre-wave absorbers.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Zdenka Medříková: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Viktorie Víchová:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Josef Kašík:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Ivo Medřík:** Investigation, Methodology. **Ondřej Malina:** Writing – original draft, Investigation.

Data availability statement

Data supporting this study are openly available from ZENODO at 10.5281/zenodo.14800594.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used Perplexity in order to grammatically correct the text. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtchem.2025.102809>.

Data availability

I have shared the link to my data in data availability statement.

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